

Synthesis, thermal, electrical and biological studies of some Schiff base complexes

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Complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} with Schiff bases derived from the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone with *p*-phenylenediamine (H₂L¹/H₂L²) have been prepared. The antibacterial activities of the ligands and their complexes have been evaluated. The kinetic parameters of decomposition have also been evaluated by both Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth methods. D.C. electrical conductivity of the complexes has been studied.

Metal complexes of Schiff bases are studied extensively due to their synthetic flexibility, selectivity and sensitivity towards the central metal atom. The Schiff base ligands resulting from the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone with some diamines have been reported to form complexes with transition metal ions^{1,2}. Literature survey revealed no study on the trivalent chromium, manganese, iron and aluminum complexes with the above mentioned Schiff bases. Hence, the present study was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The Schiff base ligands were prepared by general condensation method and characterized by elemental analysis as well as TLC, IR and ¹H NMR studies. The Schiff base complexes are coloured grey black to creamy white. All the complexes are stable in air for extended periods of time. They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents and sparingly soluble in DMF. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis, suggesting 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry (Table 1). The solids do not melt sharply but with decomposition.

The infrared spectra of the ligands showed a broad band at around 2900 cm⁻¹ (intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH), which disappeared in the complexes as hydrogen is replaced by the metal³. The shift of ν (phenolic CO) from 1270 to 1285 cm⁻¹ supports this view. The strong ligand band at 1620–1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) is lowered by 20–30 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen of the Schiff bases⁴. The bands at 480 and 545 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{M-N} and

ν_{M-O} , respectively. Appearance of new bands at 1570, 800 and 600 cm⁻¹ in the complexes of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} confirms the presence of coordinated water. In the Mn^{III} complexes, bands at 1545 and 1265 cm⁻¹ are due to the asym. and sym. COO stretching frequencies, respectively, in acetato complex. The difference of 280 cm⁻¹ between the two bands and their positions indicate monodentate nature of the acetato group⁵.

Table 1. Physical data of complexes

Compd. Metal % :	Elec. cond. (σ) ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	E_a eV	Activation energy, kJ mol ⁻¹	
			FC	SW
Cr-L ¹ (11.20 (11.29))	4.4 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.498	26.12	23.91
Cr-L ² (10.56 (11.06))	4.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.309	30.42	28.42
Mn-L ¹ (11.75 (11.80))	7.0 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.362	26.12	24.35
Mn-L ² (11.21 (11.63))	6.3 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.452	29.41	27.01
Fe-L ¹ (11.98 (12.02))	4.9 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.610	32.46	30.30
Fe-L ² (10.05 (12.02))	8.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.645	34.03	34.00
Al-L ¹ (6.50 (6.85))	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.430	28.12	26.90
Al-L ² (5.20 (5.50))	9.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.480	29.35	28.43

The electronic spectra of the Cr^{III} complexes exhibit two bands at 16000–16200 and 21900–22200 cm⁻¹ which are assignable to ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{2g} and ⁴A_{2g} → ²T_{1g} transitions,

respectively. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio is in the range 1.32–1.37, which is very close to the value of 1.42 obtained for pure octahedral Cr^{III} complexes⁴. The observed magnetic moments of the Cr^{III} complexes (3.92, 3.88 B.M.) are suggestive of normal moment for an octahedral stereochemistry.

The Mn^{III} complexes show an intense charge transfer band at around 23000 cm⁻¹ and a broad band at around 18180 cm⁻¹. Usually the spin-free Mn^{III} complexes⁶ with octahedral geometry give one charge transfer band around 25000 cm⁻¹ and a spin-allowed *d-d* transition band ${}^5E_{2g} \rightarrow {}^5T_{2g}$ around 20000 cm⁻¹. In the present complexes, the band around 18180 cm⁻¹ is assignable to the *d-d* transition. This broad band occurring at lower frequency with increased intensity indicates the lowering of symmetry from the octahedral configuration a square-pyramidal structure seems to be the most probable one in which O₂N₂ moiety forms the basal plane and the acetate group coordinated at axial position⁷. The magnetic moment value (4.81, 4.88 B.M.) of the complexes are very close to the values expected for a high-spin complexes with four unpaired electrons. Electronic spectra of the Fe^{III} complexes show bands at 14867–18833, 22691–24315 and 31876–32300 cm⁻¹. The first two bands may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (4G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions, respectively, for an octahedral stereochemistry⁸. The third band may be due the ligand-to-metal charge transfer. The effective magnetic moment values (5.49–6.10 B.M.) for the complexes are in the range expected for a spin-free octahedral Fe^{III} system. The Al^{III} complexes are found to be diamagnetic. The diffuse reflectance spectra did not show any band in the visible region. Therefore, on the basis of the data a polymeric structure could be assigned to these complexes.

The thermal studies indicate that complexes decompose in two steps after dehydration. The loss of two coordinated water molecules takes place at around 140° for Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III} atom. The first step of decomposition is fast as compared to the second step. This may be due to the fact that the non-coordinated part of the ligand decomposes first (250–290°), while the actually coordinated part decomposes later and finally at 650° forming metallic oxide⁹. No attempt was made to characterize the products formed at the end of each steps. To obtain the relative thermal stabilities of the various complexes the method described by Sharp-Wentworth¹⁰ and Freeman-Carroll¹¹ were adopted and the values which are comparable are summarized in Table 1. Since the plots are straight lines, the rate of the reaction is believed to be one over the entire range of decomposition. The complexes were found to be thermally more stable than the corresponding Schiff base ligands and decomposed in the range 285–335°.

The d.c. electrical conductivity of the complexes were studied over a wide range of temperature. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relationship $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp - E_a / kT$, where σ_0 is a constant, E_a is activation energy and k is Boltzmann constant. Over a wide range of temperature (60–220°), linear dependence of $\log \sigma = f(10^3/T)$ was observed, which confirms a semiconducting behavior of these complexes¹². The low value of electrical conductivity may be attributed to low molecular weight due to which the extent of conjugation becomes low or undesirable morphology due to pressing of the samples into hard brittle pellet form.

The ligands and their metal complexes were studied for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureous*, *Klebsiella* and *Bacillus* 19 using disc-diffusion method. The Fe and Mn complexes showed a fair biological activity, while the Cr and Al complexes were moderately active against all bacteria. However, the ligands showed a poorer inhibitory effect than their complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. grade. 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone were prepared according to literature methods. *p*-Phenylenediamine (E. Merck) was used. Mn(OAc)₃·2H₂O was prepared¹³ by the oxidation of Mn(OAc)₂·4H₂O. Elemental analyses were performed at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Metal contents were estimated using standard methods¹⁴. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) at R.S.I.C., Chandigarh, and diffuse reflectance spectra at I.I.T., Chennai. Magnetic measurements were carried out by the Gouy method at room temperature. The magnetometer was calibrated using Hg[Co(NCS)₄]. Diamagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants. Thermal studies were done with a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 thermobalance in air with a heating rate 10° min⁻¹. The d.c. electrical conductivity was measured by voltage drop technique using a microvoltmeter.

The synthesis and characterization of ligands H₂L¹ and H₂L² have been reported earlier¹⁵.

Synthesis of complexes : To a boiling solution of the ligand (0.002 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), appropriate metal salt (CrCl₃·6H₂O, Mn(OAc)₃·2H₂O, FeCl₃·6H₂O and AlSO₄; 0.002 mol) solution was added. In the case of the Mn^{III} complex, methanol was used in place of ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath 2–3 h. The resulting solid was washed with hot water, ethanol and methanol. The metal complexes were dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator.

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